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LANGUAGE ANXIETY AMONG PAKISTANI UNDERGRADUATE EFL LEARNERS: A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Language anxiety has been a huge obstacle in the learning process, particularly for undergraduate students, as English is taught as a second or foreign language in Pakistan. This study explored the key anxiety factors that hinder learners' performance and negatively impact their academic careers, as many students experience foreign language anxiety in the classroom. Data were gathered through an online survey questionnaire consisting of open and closed-ended questions from BS English students, both males and females, studying at National University of Modern Languages Islamabad, Multan Campus. This research utilized a mixed-methods approach and designed the questionnaire based on the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS). The responses were analyzed employing Statistical Package for Social Sciences to determine mean, median, mode and standard deviations. Results revealed that the majority of students experience language anxiety during English language classes similarly various factors affect their learning outcomes. The current study also discussed participants' responses and offered suggestions to alleviate their anxiety.

Keywords: Foreign Language Anxiety, Anxiety Variables, English as Foreign Language Learners, English Language Classroom, Undergraduate Students

Introduction

Language plays a pivotal role in communication, developing relationships, and enhancing connections in society. It establishes a bridge between different cultures and helps speakers express their thoughts simply and convey their messages to others. An individual acquires their first language at home, whereas several factors are involved when learning a second language. According to Scovel (1978), the learner's motivation and emotional reactions are significant factors that influence second language acquisition. Anxiety and motivation are two important predictors of second language learning (SLL) (Dornyei, 1994).

Language anxiety refers to learning a target language as a second or foreign language, which is influenced by learners' reactions, emotions, and specific circumstances. According to Horwitz E. K. (1986), anxiety is related to other general types that arise while learning a target language. For instance, a student may experience anxiety when speaking in a second language, and additional anxiety might occur during testing. (Swain, 2013) , examined that language learning is not merely restricted to mental functions; it also involves emotional processes.

E.K. Horwitz (1986) introduced Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) to measure learner's anxiety in the Foreign Language (FL) classroom. FLA has been considered as one of the main factors that constrain second language acquisition and language performance (Arnold, 1999) . Foreign Language researchers have analyzed specific variables that are responsible for influencing the learner's achievement or failure in foreign

language learning in a classroom setting. Krashen (1985) argued that anxiety is stimulated most in classrooms for second/foreign language learning. Kim (1998) observed that anxiety increases among learners in the classroom rather than in a conversational setting.

The study emphasizes English as a Second Language (ESL) or English as Foreign Language (EFL) in Pakistan, where learners are encouraged to study the English language. The official language of Pakistan is English, and it also serves as a sign of social status. It has become a need of time to learn English for acquiring jobs and expressing academic work fluently in the education department (Mansoor, 2004). Pakistani society gives importance to English as L2/FL and motivates the learners to study and speak English fluently. The students have to learn English as a second language because it has become a compulsory subject till the graduate level. Oxford (1994) claimed that second language learning is interlinked with visual and auditory stimulations in the target language.

Background of the Study

English has been regarded as a global language that is taught as L2/FL in Pakistan. The proficiency in the language is marked as academic success and intellectual competence in educational and professional settings. Learners feel pressured to improve their writing expression and fluency in the target language for effective communication. The stress leads to anxiety, creating a psychological barrier in the learning process. Pappamihiel (2002) defined language anxiety as a type of anxiety that arises during interaction in class where a learner has to speak in foreign language. However, classroom teachers can offer assistance in coping with their supportive behavior to lower the level of anxiety (Ewald, 2007). Therefore, present study aims to identify the major variables and analyze the influence of anxiety on their performance.

Literature Review

According to previous studies, anxiety in learning L2 or FL creates an impact on the learner's performance positively or negatively, e.g., (Matsuda, 2004), presents their findings that self-confidence (high or low) of the students determines the success of foreign language learning. They researched that language anxiety influences the presentation of the learners in the classroom, and it hinders achieving the desired results if self-confidence is not prominent. (Casado, 2004), examined the language anxiety in university students and found that confidence is the vital factor in learning a foreign language.

The researchers have conducted several studies to find the exact causes of FLA in different contexts. Some researchers claim that anxiety is provoked through a lack of language skills (Sparks, 2000). However, MacIntyre P.D., (1994) experimented on language learners and concluded that the students exposed to the camera were exhibiting anxiety as compared to those who were not filmed.

The students in front of the camera performed negatively because they lost confidence and forgot to utilize the learned vocabulary in their speech. The attitude of the teacher also plays a vital role in language anxiety and language learning. (Abu-Rabia, 2004) , observed that the supportive behavior of teachers alleviates the anxiety level of the students.

Language anxiety does not only relate to negative results. Marzluf (2012) stated in his sociolinguistic study in Mongolia that Mongolians do not perceive that the English language will take the place of their cultural identity and linguistic patterns; rather, they learn English to express their thoughts and anxieties to neighboring countries (e.g., China). The identity of the language learners is constructed under the factors like culture, environment, and society, while learning L2/FL. The learner constructs and reconstructs both identities while experiencing L1 and L2/FL learning. Scollon (1997) reported that students learning the English language are influenced by their culture, media, and trends, which leave visible effects on the original culture and native language that develop identities.

The previous studies have tried to prove that anxiety is a dominant factor that hinders the process of foreign language learning (Koch, 1991) , stating that the acquisition of a foreign language provides anxiety, frustration, and stress when learners are representing verbally in front of the class. Horwitz E.K (2001) suggested that language anxiety creates a negative impact on their performance.

MacIntyre P.D (1994) argued that anxiety causes hindrance in the acquisition of a foreign language. Different researches have been performed to analyze the factors influencing foreign language learning in classrooms for different languages around the world.

Statement of the Problem

The majority of the students enrolled in BS English are affected by language anxiety, leaving a pessimistic impact on communication skills especially writing abilities. The current study aims to analyze the prominent variables that are hindering the performance of learners to provide strategies to overcome language anxiety.

Scope of the Study

This research investigates variables of language anxiety in EFL learners by applying the FLCAS. It investigates major variables, including fear of negative evaluation, communication apprehension, test anxiety, and general anxiety in English class. The suggestions will provide practices for learners to improve their verbal and written expressions.

Research Objectives

This research has the following objectives:

- To identify the variable causing language anxiety in EFL learners in Pakistan
- To examine the effect on EFL learners' performance in academics

- To suggest strategies to overcome language anxiety

Research Questions

The study addresses the following questions:

1. How do the EFL learners in Pakistan suffer from language anxiety?
2. What are the major factors of language anxiety among EFL learners in Pakistan?
3. How can language anxiety be reduced among EFL learners for better performance?

Limitation

The research is limited to a single educational institution with a single department, which cannot produce generalized results. The data collected from the students might not completely express their experience and emotions about the anxiety they feel during learning EFL. The study is restricted to a classroom setting and excludes other informal language learning setups.

Delimitation

The research only focuses on the undergraduate EFL learners in Pakistan. Since this was not feasible to take all the universities and their programs into consideration, thus the researcher chose students of one Province that is Punjab and only students from one university National University of Modern Languages (NUML) Islamabad Sub-Campus Multan was taken into account for conducting research. The study analyzes language anxiety in students with less exposure to express themselves in front of an audience. It mainly examines the anxiety problems of students from a single institution and offers solutions according to their situations.

Significance of the Study

Language anxiety has been a significant issue, becoming an obstacle for EFL learners, especially in Pakistan, where English plays a dominant part in academics and professional settings. This study highlights the problems faced by undergraduates, aiming to learn English as a foreign language. It focuses on the variables that cause anxiety in the learners and the reasons for a lack of performance and communication skills. Self-confidence and overcoming barriers are essential for students to enhance their skills to achieve success in the academic field and secure career opportunities.

Research Design

This research involved a structured questionnaire based on the FLCAS developed by, E.K.Horwitz (1986) and identified the quantitative data from the respondents. The questionnaire examined the factors faced by students in learning English as L2 or FL, including fear of making mistakes, test anxiety, and inability to communicate effectively. The provided data were evaluated through statistical analysis.

Methodology

A structured online questionnaire with both quantitative and

qualitative parts has been selected to collect data from the EFL learners to examine measurable variables in this study. However, previous studies on language anxiety in foreign language learners have been conducted through a quantitative or qualitative approach. Therefore, present study explores the anxiety factors in learning EFL through quantitative and qualitative approaches that is generally known as mixed-method research.

Population

The population for this particular research consists of undergraduate students of Pakistan, enrolled in BS English at public and private sector universities. Students are learning English as FL, which might feel like language anxiety while studying and communicating. The target approach has been focused on EFL learners, who are more likely to experience problems during interactions and presentation of their work in front of the teacher and other fellows. This research provides insight into analyzing the difficulties faced by learners in their academics.

Sampling

The respondents of this study are undergraduates learning English as FL at NUML University, Multan Campus. The students were selected from the BS English department (Semesters 1st to 8th), involving both males (14) and females (36) in the research. A total of 50 participants have been selected to evaluate the quantitative data. The technique of purposive sampling has been used to analyze the language anxiety among undergraduate students. The EFL learners regularly participate in written and spoken classes, where they take part in assignments, discussions, and present their work in front of the class in English.

Data Collection Procedure

The online questionnaire survey was shared among the students of BS English at NUML University, Multan Campus. The participants were guided on how to give their consent and an honest response in the forms. The responses were collected voluntarily, and none of the respondents were forced to fill out the questionnaires. They were assured of their privacy and confidentiality, maintaining the ethical considerations. The information was only gathered to measure the language anxiety among the learners and not to target specific individuals to criticize them for not performing well during the class. The collected data was analyzed from the students who responded voluntarily.

Reasons for Selecting a Specific Research Instrument

The most renowned instrument, which has been utilized to measure language anxiety among students in the classroom, was developed by E.K. Horwitz (1986) known as FLCAS. The researchers have included the criteria to develop the questionnaire based on FLCAS, as it is well-known for its validity and reliability.

The Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale

The scale was originally designed by Horwitz but the current research used adopted version, which replaces the expression

“Foreign Language” with the “English Language” of the FLCAS to measure the language anxiety in Pakistani students. It comprises 33 statements, and each statement is measured on a five-point Likert scale, which ranges from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The higher scores show a high level of anxiety, whereas the lower scores show a low level of anxiety in EFL learners. The four factors contribute to measuring the anxiety level among the participants, including the fear of negative evaluation, communication apprehension, test anxiety, and anxiety of English classes. The last variable is suitable in the Pakistani context, where English has been taught as a second language/ foreign language, and students mostly suffer from anxiety in the English language in comparison to other languages.

Piloting and Validation:

The questionnaire survey was shared with the students of BS English at Bahauddin Zakariya University (BZU), Multan, for piloting and validation. The responses were analyzed to check the validity and reliability of the instrument. This step ensured the relevance of questions, which proved that this questionnaire is suitable for the target population.

Data Analysis

The responses from the participants are represented in tables and graphs to display the results conducted from the research. Table 1 shows the background of the participants (i.e., demographical information), including the categories of age, gender, and semesters they are studying in their current session. The tabular form of the result is presented as follows:

Table 1: Participants’ Background Information

Information	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	19-20	20	40.0
	21-22	13	26.0
	23-24	17	34.0
Gender	Male	14	28.0
	Female	36	72.0
Semesters	1 st -2 nd	16	32.0
	3 rd -4 th	10	20.0
	5 th -6 th	11	22.0
	7 th -8 th	13	26.0

Figure 1. Age of Respondents

Fig.1. represents that most students in early semesters of the session may experience language anxiety, but they can suffer from it at any phase of the learning process. Some students find difficulty at the beginning stage, whereas other students lose confidence at the difficult stage. Fig.2. presents the gender of the respondents who have taken part in this research and expressed their concerns related to the language anxiety:

Figure 2. Gender of Respondents

Figure 3. Semesters of BS English

Fig.3. illustrates the graphical representation of the participants enrolled in different semesters. The ratio of students in the 1st

semester is higher as compared to the other semesters. Fig.4 reflects the number of respondents who have suffered from foreign language anxiety. The ratio of anxious learners is higher in comparison to those who have not experienced any kind of anxiety during their session, as it is evident in the chart below:

Figure 4. Anxiety Experienced by Learners

Quantitative Data Analysis

The responses gathered from the online questionnaire have been examined by using SPSS to derive the mean, mode, median, and standard deviation of the provided data. Table 2 shows the analysis of 33 statements that are based on FLCAS to measure the anxiety level among the learners:

Table 2: Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS)

Statements	Mean	Mode	Median	Standard Deviation
I never feel quite sure of myself when I am speaking in my English class.	2.84	2.00	3.00	1.07
I don't worry about making mistakes in my English Class	3.28	4.00	4.00	1.02
I tremble when I know that I'm going to be called on in English class.	3.00	2.00	3.00	1.08
It frightens me when I don't understand what the teacher is saying in English.	3.64	4.00	4.00	1.19
It wouldn't bother me at all to take more English classes.	2.44	2.00	2.00	.87
During English class, I find myself thinking about things that have nothing to do with the course.	2.64	2.00	2.00	.95
I keep thinking that the other students are better at English than I am.	2.68	2.00	2.00	.95

I am usually at ease during tests in my English class.	2.72	2.00 ^a	3.00	.89
I start to panic when I have to speak without preparation in English class.	2.64	2.00	2.00	1.04
I worry about consequences of failing my English class.	3.00	2.00	3.00	1.08
I don't understand why some people get so upset over English classes.	2.76	2.00	2.00	.93
In English class, I can get so nervous I forget things I know.	3.04	2.00	3.00	1.06
It embarrasses me to volunteer answers in English class.	2.88	2.00 ^a	3.00	1.17
I would not be nervous speaking English with native speakers.	3.20	2.00	3.00	1.08
I get upset when I don't understand what the teacher is correcting.	3.24	4.00	3.00	.88
Even if I am well prepared for English class, I feel anxious about it.	3.04	3.00	3.00	1.04
I often feel like not going to my English class.	3.32	3.00	3.00	.95
I feel confident when I speak in my English class.	2.80	2.00	3.00	1.08
I am afraid that my English teacher is ready to correct every mistake I make.	3.00	2.00 ^a	3.00	1.04
I can feel my heart pounding when I am going to be called on in my English class.	2.60	2.00	2.00	.96
The more I study for an English test, the more confused I get.	3.48	4.00	4.00	1.00
I don't feel pressure to prepare very well for English class.	2.88	2.00	2.00	1.09
I always feel that the other students speak English better than I do.	2.52	2.00	2.00	1.00
I feel very self-conscious about speaking English in front of other students.	2.52	2.00	2.00	1.12
English class moves so quickly I worry about getting left behind.	3.24	4.00	3.00	1.05
I feel more tense and nervous in my English class than in my other classes.	3.36	4.00	4.00	1.04
I get nervous and confused when I am speaking in my English class.	2.84	2.00	3.00	1.07

When I am on my way to English class, I feel very sure and relaxed.	2.76	2.00	3.00	.93
I get nervous when I don't understand every word the English teacher says.	3.16	4.00	3.00	1.07
I feel overwhelmed by the number of rules you have to learn to speak English.	2.84	2.00 ^a	3.00	.99
I am afraid that the other students will laugh at me when I speak English.	2.96	2.00	3.00	1.24
I would probably feel comfortable around the native speakers of English.	3.04	3.00	3.00	1.14
I get nervous when the English teacher ask questions which I haven't prepared in advance.	2.96	3.00	3.00	1.11

Qualitative Data Analysis

The previous research has concluded that language anxiety creates a negative effect on foreign language learning. The learners are unable to perform well and communicate in English when they feel anxious in the classroom. The research examined the four anxiety variables through a structured online questionnaire among the male and female EFL learners at the undergraduate level. These variables are connected with other factors that influence the learning outcome, including poor academic background, strict classroom environment, nervousness, lack of confidence, and fluency, etc.

Fear of Negative Evaluation

The participants responded that they feel embarrassed when making mistakes in the classroom. They have a fear of getting a negative evaluation, which will result in discouragement. They consider that it leaves a negative image about them among other fellows. It leads to demotivation in participants as they consider themselves mediocre in front of others, thinking that students in the class will judge and make fun of their mistakes. As one respondent replies upon asking if they feel embarrassed or judged after getting evaluated:

I did feel judged and that negatively affected my confidence.

This creates anxiety in the EFL learners as they lose confidence after a negative evaluation. Their confidence is shattered in front of the class when presenting their work because they think that they will be judged for making mistakes. They also fear that teachers will judge and think they are an average student, making several mistakes. Another participant responded:

I am afraid that when I make mistakes in English class and my confidence is very low Thus, learners feel anxious when they observe that they are getting judged on their performance; they lose confidence and determination to improve their mistakes.

Communication Apprehension

The major aspect of learning any language is the ability to comprehend and communicate with others. The anxiety factor has been mostly prominent in the speaking skills of the learners because they feel hesitant in conveying the message in the target language. Many EFL learners become nervous in classroom settings when they are invited to engage in discussions and deliver presentations in English. On the participant's response that they feel:

Nervous, distracted by just seeing how they react to me, to just speaking or saying anything in English.

Students may hesitate to speak in English, considering their past mistakes and fear of getting judged. This variable becomes a barrier to fluency and affects the development of better performance. When other fellows make fun of mistakes or mispronunciation of the learners, they lose confidence. One participant said:

The anxiety of mispronouncing some words catches you. And it's quite common that they laugh at one whose English is not that good.

This reason leads to avoiding communicating in English, and learners switch to their mother tongue. They experience nervousness and are reluctant to express their views in a foreign language as they are not fully prepared to speak fluently.

Text Anxiety

It is a general variable that creates anxiety among EFL learners and mainly impacts their writing skills and academic performance. This includes stress and fear of taking quizzes and written exams, as their writing expressions are evaluated through sentence structure, vocabulary, and grammar rules. Due to a lack of vocabulary, some learners face a situation of anxiety because they cannot write the answers with appropriate words. Another respondent highlighted this aspect: *We feel confused and find no words for communication*. The anxiety creates a barrier to concentration and recalling memorized data. Even if the student is well-prepared, the stress of attempting wrong answers in the test leads to the fear of failure and negative marking. This factor decreases the confidence level of learners, and they avoid taking tests in class, which also affects their confidence. Another participant expressed:

There are mixed emotions and thoughts, mostly negative ones, about how I am going to perform.

Test anxiety may hinder the learning process as students will feel less motivated to participate and practice to develop their writing skills. Therefore, they cannot express their ideas in their style because they develop a fear of getting judged and making mistakes lowers their confidence.

General Anxiety in English Classes

General anxiety refers to the feeling of stress and nervousness in the classroom experienced by EFL learners. This type of anxiety is

not specific to tests or communication barriers; rather, it affects the overall performance of the students in an academic setting. Learners may feel pressurized to perform better, overcome the fear of making mistakes, and get judged by fellow students. They find complications in understanding the concept when the teacher delivers a complete lecture in English. Stress and anxiety affect their listening and reading skills, resulting in a lack of confidence and escaping eye contact. Learning English as FL becomes a difficult task, as one participant said: *There are many words that I don't know the meaning, so I try to learn every difficult word.*

Anxiety creates a negative effect on the learning strategies of learners, and they become hesitant to ask questions during the class. They are not confident enough to approach the teacher and seek guidance. Thus, they lose confidence and motivation because of classroom anxiety. One of the major problems arises from inadequate support from class fellows, which causes embarrassment among the learners. One participant responded: *The major problem that I and every other student face is the fear of getting judged based on our speaking skills, our accent and pronunciation, and a lot more.*

Overall, general anxiety is mostly influenced by factors involving fear of judgment, negative evaluation, making mistakes, and embarrassment in communicating in the target language. These prominent factors are involved in losing confidence and determination to contribute to academic activities in the classroom.

Discussion

The findings revealed that the majority of EFL learners experience foreign language anxiety in the classroom due to different factors. The highest mean value identified in the results was linked with English class anxiety, where a learner cannot fully gain understanding of the concepts when the lecture is delivered in the target language only (M=3.64, SD=1.19); on the contrary, the lowest mean value was recorded where students were motivated to take more English classes (M=2.44, SD=0.87).

Some of the variables mainly deal with communication barriers and anxiety of attempting a test in fear of getting a negative evaluation. Another reason includes a lack of confidence, which makes the student unable to give a better performance in academics, with the stress of being judged and negatively criticized by the teacher and fellow learners. This will cause an immediate decline in their motivation level, and they will lose interest in learning English as FL. When students feel the pressure of presenting without mistakes, they step back and do not take part in any of the activities and events to avoid embarrassment, they might have to go through making mistakes in front of the audience.

Communicating in the target language has been the most stressful aspect for foreign language learners. Students speak in their native language at home, with their fellows, and in other public places, but the sudden pressure to speak in foreign language

in educational institutes or any other professional settings leads to anxiety and stress. According to Kondo (2004), language anxiety directly affects the academic performance of learners. Gregersen (2005) also shared the same views that anxious learners avoid taking tests instead of learning from their mistakes. Students who learn and practice to achieve better outcomes are more likely to overcome their fears in learning a foreign language. They get proficient in a second/foreign language and thus, they have a lower level of anxiety during communication, tests, and presentations.

Another major variable in constructing language anxiety among EFL learners is the fear of negative evaluation. Some learners face problems while writing and expressing concepts in English, more than speaking in the target language; therefore, they are anxious about making mistakes and getting judged. On the contrary, students who are regular in taking their sessions and practicing have experienced low levels of foreign language anxiety as they feel confident after sharing their concerns with their instructors (Carreira, 2006). In the context of Pakistan, the English language has been given much importance in academic and professional environments. Therefore, learning and speaking fluently has been made a requirement for job interviews and presentations during the learning sessions. Despite being multilingual, students often hesitate in the English language if they are not well prepared before the test.

Various other variables hinder the improvement of the language learning process, such as previous educational background. There are possibilities that students might not have participated in extra-curricular activities that will boost their confidence, or the level of proficiency might be low in the English subject, which causes anxiety and stress among the learners because they have not interacted and communicated with fellow learners in the target language. The previous research also provides similar data for FLCAS. This study primarily highlighted the major variables that become the barrier for learners, and thus provided the most possible suggestions that can be effortlessly implemented in the classroom by the teacher. The assistance of instructors will provide a better understanding of the concepts and help them overcome anxiety.

Conclusion

The study conducted at NUML University, Multan Campus concluded that the majority of the students enrolled in the department of English at the undergraduate level experience anxiety and stress in studying this subject as a foreign language. Findings demonstrate that language anxiety has been a common factor that becomes a barrier in the effective learning process, especially during the early semesters of the session. The majority of the students lack confidence and have test anxiety at the beginning level of the study, which can be overcome through practice and communication. The research measured different

levels of anxiety among the learners by applying FLCAS, which is specifically designed for academic settings. Through this scale, the present study analyzed four major factors, including fear of negative evaluation, communication apprehension, test anxiety, and general language anxiety that students face in the classroom. The major reason for the stress arises from nervousness in front of the teacher and other classmates during presentations, discussions, and tests. Several other researchers also claimed that language anxiety affects their academic outcomes (Wei, 2013).

Learners experience the fear of criticism and judgment for their mistakes while speaking or taking the test. Therefore, a supportive classroom environment should be provided to learners for better outcomes. It will encourage them to participate in debates, discussions, and present their work confidently in front of their classmates. Teachers can help EFL learners by paying close attention to them so that they can offer assistance to overcome their anxieties.

Suggestions for Overcoming Language Anxiety

The following strategies are suggested to overcome language anxiety for EFL learners in the classroom:

1. Fluency in speaking should be improved through practice and interaction with other learners in English.
2. Negative criticism should be discouraged, and students should be provided with a supportive environment where they can improve their skills.
3. Group activities help diminish pressure and encourage learners to collaborate to share their problems and find solutions through different perspectives.
4. Students with anxiety can initiate speaking in smaller groups and then gradually gain confidence to express their views in front of the class.
5. Learners should be given feedback without making them feel embarrassed and judged.
6. The teacher should encourage every student to engage with everyone with support rather than laughing at the ones making mistakes.
7. Supportive classmates can also help reduce anxiety by offering assistance in difficult situations.
8. Anxiety level should be reduced through teaching methods that will make the concepts easy for learners to understand.
9. Teachers should give time to students for preparation and then for confidently presenting their work.
10. Students should share their anxiety with teachers so they may help them overcome the fear and stress of academic pressure.

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